

Two-dimension ordinations of 330 cultivars observed in Hangzhou, China, 1983.

Possibility of transferring apomixis from sorghum to rice

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Apomixis can be exploited for the fixation of heterosis in hybrid rice. However, no cultivated or wild rice species with apomictic modes of reproduction are known. The only cereal in which a high frequency of facultative apomixis (80%) has been exploited is grain sorghum. We attempted intergeneric transfer of apomixis using protoplast fusion.

An embryogenic cell suspension culture LB-1 of rice variety T309 is available as a source of protoplasts at Nottingham University. Sorghum protoplasts can be isolated from leaves. Using standard procedures, protoplasts from the LB-1 suspension culture of T309 and mesophyll protoplasts from the apomictic sorghum line R473 were

isolated. Rice protoplasts were vitally stained with fluorescein diacetate (FDA) to facilitate identification.

After washing in electrofusion solution, protoplasts were mixed in a ratio of 1:1. Fusion was accomplished using Watts and King electrofusion equipment. Alignment of protoplasts was obtained in an AC field of 500 KHz volts for 20 s. A high frequency (6-8%) protoplast fusion was obtained with a 400 V DC pulse for 2 μ s. The mixture of unfused protoplasts and heterokaryons was plated in sea plaque agarose in petri plates, with the position of heterokaryons marked with ink dots.

Within 10-12 d, the heterokaryons had formed walls and undergone 3 divisions. There was no subsequent development.

Further manipulation of the cultural conditions (prior conditioning of the medium with T309 callus, change in the composition of the medium, nurse culture, etc.) could help realize regenerated somatic hybrids. In similar intergeneric somatic hybrids, the

genome of one parent is eliminated. It should be easy to screen progeny of regenerated rice plants for apomixis. □

Receptivity of exerted stigmas

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Experimental evidence suggests that exerted stigma traits, in particular its receptivity (probability of fertilization and seed set on spikelets with exerted stigma by artificial pollination after flowering) in CMS lines would increase outcrossing rates. We analyzed cultivars Xie-qing-zao (completely male sterile) and selections 25154 and 97154 (both partially male sterile) with exerted stigma, and Er-jiu-qing with non-exerted stigma for stigma receptivity to alien pollen at Linshui, Hainan, China, in spring 1984.

Exserted stigma showed higher receptivity within 1-2 d after flowering (see table). Seed set after pollination was in direct proportion to percentage exserted stigma (PES), and seed set was higher on spikelets with double exserted stigma than on those with single exserted stigma. With pollination the second day after flowering, seed set on spikelets with double and single exserted stigma was 0 in Xieqing-zao A, 20% in 25154, and 51% in 97154, indicating marked differences in stigma receptivity.

Receptivity was also closely associated with stigmatic characteristics. Stigma breadth was 0.36 mm in 25154 and 0.37 mm in 97154, but only 0.30 mm in Xieqing-zao. Xieqing-zao stigmas were slender and less branchy, easily damaged when protruded, and dried quickly after flowering, losing receptivity.

Percentage seed set on spikelets with

Exserted stigma and seed set under artificial pollination by day after flowering.^a Linshui, Hainan, China, 1984 spring.

Cultivar	Pollination day after flowering ^b	Spikelets (no.)	Exserted stigma (%)	Seed set (%) in spikelets			
				Total (exserted and nonexserted)	Exserted stigma	Double exserted stigma	Single exserted stigma
97154 sel.	Check	315	59.4	2.9	4.8	7.7	3.3
	Same day	241	63.9	45.6	71.4	70.5	71.8
	Day 1	217	68.2	32.3	47.3	80.0	35.2
	Day 2	240	62.9	32.1	51.0	72.5	43.2
25154 sel. (artificially emasculated)	Check	230	32.6	0	0	0	0
	Day 1	125	53.6	23.2	43.3	73.3	34.6
	Day 2	121	46.3	9.1	19.6	33.3	17.0
Xieqing-zao	Check	105	18.1	0	0	0	0
	Day 1	129	29.5	8.5	29.0	71.4	19.4
	Day 2	93	23.7	0	0	0	0
	Day 3	83	21.7	0	0	0	0

^aEr-jiu-qing had no seed set after pollination on the same day, day 1, and day 2. ^bCheck = no pollination.

exserted stigma 2 d after flowering may be used as an index of receptivity of exserted stigma. Stigma exertion makes

it possible to breed CMS lines with higher PES and to improve the outcrossing rate. □

Yield potential

Rice heterosis for panicle branching, spikelet number, and vascular bundle number

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Heterosis for 9 quantitative characters was assessed in crosses using 7 high density (HD)-grain parents (at least 30% of the grains having specific gravity greater than 1.20) and 2 low density (LD)-grain parents.

Estimates of overall degree and direction of heterosis were positive and significant for number of secondary branches, number of spikelets on secondary branches, and number of inner vascular bundle, indicating dominance of higher values (Table 1). Heterosis was negative for number of spikelets on tertiary branches and number of outer vascular bundles where genes of lower count dominated. Low or nonsignificant heterosis for other characters may be due to little genetic

Table 1. Overall parental and F₁ means and deviation for 9 quantitative yield characters. IRRI, 1988.

Character	Mean of parents (P)	Mean of F ₁ s (F ₁)	Overall heterosis (F ₁ -P)	LSD (0.05)
Primary branches (no.)	11.31	11.27	-0.04	0.25
Secondary branches (no.)	33.09	34.96	1.87	1.56
Tertiary branches (no.)	0.91	0.64	-0.27	0.29
Spikelets on primary branches (no.)	66.64	65.53	-1.11	2.79
Spikelets on secondary branches (no.)	113.40	120.74	7.34	7.29
Spikelets on tertiary branches (no.)	2.40	1.44	-0.96	0.86
Total spikelets (no.)	182.30	187.74	5.44	8.21
Inner vascular bundles (no.)	23.12	23.98	0.86	0.52
Outer vascular bundles (no.)	23.43	21.94	-1.49	0.86

interactions or differences among parents.

Values for individual F₁ families differed from overall estimates for different characters, showing positive, negative, or no heterosis (Table 2). The F₁ means deviated conspicuously from parental and midparental values, indicating involvement of nonadditive gene action in the expression of most characters.

Substantial heterosis in the desirable direction was observed in number of primary branches, number of spikelets on primary branches, inner vascular

bundles, and outer vascular bundles. Three crosses among HD-grain parents and one cross between HD- and LD-grain parents exhibited positive heterosis for number of primary branches. The cross P2/P9 manifested positive heterosis for all other characters. Positive heterosis for total number of spikelets was observed in all crosses except P3/P8, through spikelet numbers on primary, secondary, and tertiary branches. Number of inner vascular bundles exhibited positive heterosis in most crosses, but the reverse was true for number of outer vascular bundles.